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IFC Whisperer: Querying Building Information Models with Large Language Models and IFC-based Knowledge Graphs

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Abstract. The transition to sustainable and resource-efficient built environments requires systematic access to semantic building information to improve performance management. However, current Building Information Modeling (BIM) practices face challenges in making geometric, topological, and material data easily accessible. Extracting critical information, such as material properties, often requires expert knowledge and complex parsing, limiting the effective use of BIM for material lifecycle management and waste reduction. To address this challenge, this paper presents a novel approach that leverages graph-based retrieval and large language models (LLMs) to enable intuitive BIM interaction through natural language queries. The proposed pipeline transforms Industry Foundation Classes (IFC) data into a dynamic knowledge graph and then uses LLM to translate queries (for example, 'Which materials in the building can be recycled?') into structured graph searches. Comprising three key steps: (1) extraction of entities from IFC models, (2) construction of knowledge graphs, and (3) translation of LLM-supported queries, the framework facilitates more accessible decision-making in sustainable building practices, particularly for material life cycle management and waste reduction.

1. Introduction

The transition toward sustainable and resource-efficient built environments requires advanced digital platforms to support informed decision-making in material utilization and lifecycle sustainability. The Industry Foundation Classes (IFC) schema has become de facto non-proprietary for BIM data exchange [1], capturing rich structural and spatial details for numerous building elements and materials. However, despite its versatility, extracting targeted information, such as recyclability metrics, remains challenging without specialized expertise or complex queries [2]. This difficulty arises from the inherently static object-centric structure of the IFC, which often lacks the higher-level semantic relationships essential for evaluating sustainability aspects such as material circularity, embodied carbon, and energy performance. As a result, researchers and practitioners seek more flexible, semantically enriched methods for dynamic data exploration and advanced sustainability assessments. This paper addresses this need by proposing a framework that leverages graph-based data representations, ontologies, and knowledge graphs to support granular building data queries and analytics.

2. Background

While IFC provides a standardized format for representing building data, extracting specific information remains challenging due to its hierarchical structure and lack of explicit relationships between sustainability-related attributes. Issues include:

- Difficulty integrating geometric/topological data with lifecycle details
- Accessibility barriers for non-experts lacking IFC query expertise
- Fragmented data across disciplines, requiring extensive manual interpretation

A more intuitive semantic enrichment process and querying approach are needed to address these challenges, allowing users to interact with BIM data without technical expertise.

2.1. Graph-based approach for information retrieval from IFC models

Typical Retrieval-Augmented Generation (RAG) systems rely on approximate similarity search in a vector database [3]. Although effective for unstructured text, it struggles with the inherently structured nature of IFC, which encodes intricate relationships among building elements. In contrast, a graph-based approach explicitly models IFC entities and their interconnections, providing more reliable retrieval and structured responses [4]. LLMs such as GPT-4 and LLaMA often hallucinate due to limited domain knowledge and proprietary data constraints [5, 6, 7]. Although RAG mitigates this by integrating retrieval, it typically focuses on unstructured text and overlooks the interconnected structure of IFC data [8, 9]. This can lead to redundant text snippets [10], a lack of global context, and an inability to utilize IFC hierarchies effectively [11]. The proposed graph-based retrieval strategy retrieves subgraphs or communities, embedding semantic links among IFC materials, spatial elements, and lifecycle attributes. Unlike standard LLM queries that treat IFC as flat text, this approach leverages the existing structured data, making it possible to extract specific attributes (e.g., material volumes) more accurately. As illustrated in Figure 1, this not only enhances query precision but also improves explainability and supports better interoperability for sustainability-focused IFC-driven decision-making.

Figure 1. Comparing Direct LLM and Graph-based approach for volume calculation in IFC data: Directly inputting an IFC file into an LLM may result in inaccurate or vague responses, as LLM lacks structured reasoning for geometric calculations. The graph-based approach, however, leverages explicit entity relationships, accurately extracting dimensions and computing volumes from the structured IFC graph for precise results.

3. Methodology

Figure 2. A Framework for IFC Graph-Based Query Processing

3.1. Semantic Enrichment

Although IFC typically describes building elements (such as slabs and walls) in terms of geometry and a few basic properties, it may not capture the specialized details required for advanced tasks such as recycling analyses, lifecycle assessments, or sustainability evaluations. To address this limitation, domain-specific attributes can be added to IFC entities in the form of custom property sets or extended classes. Examples of such semantic enrichments include material composition data, performance metrics like global warming potential (GWP), measured contaminant levels, and any other application-relevant information that goes beyond the default IFC specification. By embedding this extra layer of semantics, the enriched IFC models are better prepared for comprehensive analyses that rely on precise property definitions and interrelationships among building elements.

3.2. IFC Data Processing & Graph Representation

Once an IFC model has been enriched with additional properties, it is parsed to identify entities such as building components, materials, and spatial connections. These elements are then mapped into a knowledge graph, where each entity becomes a node, and the relationships among them (for instance, which materials a component contains or how different entities form part of a larger assembly) are represented as edges. This graph-based structure preserves IFC data's inherent hierarchical and relational nature while making it more amenable to query-driven exploration. By traversing the graph, users can combine multiple pieces of information, such as material properties, spatial hierarchy, or geometric constraints, to perform nuanced analyses without manually dissecting complex IFC schemas.

3.3. Query Processing with LLMs

To enable intuitive access to the knowledge graph, LLMs are employed to convert user questions into structured graph queries. This is done by crafting prompts that specify the graph schema, property naming conventions, and example queries. When a user poses a question in natural language, the LLM references these prompts to generate the appropriate syntax (for example, a Cypher or SPARQL query) that retrieves the needed nodes and edges. By providing the LLM with both template queries and expected outcomes, it is guided to mirror the underlying structure of the IFC data accurately. As a result, the system can, for example, retrieve specific assemblies, check material properties, and filter elements by particular attributes according to the relationships defined in the graph (see Figure 2 and Algorithm 1). This approach leverages the strengths of LLMs in understanding natural language while retaining the precision and clarity inherent in a graph-based representation of building information.

Algorithm 1 IFC to Graph Workflow with AI Query Generation

```

1: procedure IngestIFCFile(ifcFilePath)           ▷ Extract IFC entities and build the graph
2:   CreateElementsAndRelationships(ifcFilePath)
3: end procedure
4: procedure TranslateQuery(userQuery)           ▷ Generate query from natural language
5:   promptContext ← {schema : schemaInfo, examples : exampleQueries}
6:   generatedQuery ← GenerateQueries(userQuery, promptContext)
7:   return generatedQuery
8: end procedure
9: procedure ExecuteAndExplain(generatedQuery, userQuery)   ▷ Run query and
   produce a natural language explanation
10:  rawResults ← graphDB.RunQuery(generatedQuery)
11:  structuredResults ← ProcessQueryResults(rawResults)
12:  explanationContext ← {userQuery, generatedQuery, structuredResults}
13:  Answer ← GenerateExplanation(explanationContext)
14:  return {structuredResults, Answer}
15: end procedure

```

4. Case Study: Digital Delivery of Concrete

In this case study, we map Digital Delivery Ticket (DDT) parameters—including circular potential data—onto IFC and define new properties where none previously existed (see Figure 3). We then illustrate how DDT data stored in IFC translates into a knowledge graph, followed by example queries for key attributes (e.g., delivery dates, volumes, recycled content) and their expected results.

Figure 3. Mapping Concrete Delivery Ontology. This schematic shows how DDT fields (e.g., manufacturer, recycled content) extend the standard IFC structure.

4.1. Implementation

After enriching the IFC model with DDT properties, we used IfcOpenShell to extract entities like IfcWall, IfcMaterial, and IfcPropertySet. These were converted into nodes and edges in Neo4j, preserving references to both the core IFC schema (e.g., HAS PROPERTY, madeOf) and newly introduced fields (e.g., RecycledAggregatePercentage). The system then leveraged LLMs to translate user queries—specified in everyday language—into Cypher statements tailored to these nodes and relationships. This prompting process followed the same template-based guidance discussed in Section 3.3, but it specifically highlighted the DDT-related properties (for example, Manufacturer or OrderNumber) so the LLM could incorporate them into generated queries without hallucination.

4.2. IFC-Derived DDT Data

Figure 3 outlines how DDT parameters (such as manufacturer details, order numbers, GWP values, and the percentage of recycled aggregates) map onto IFC classes, while Figure 4 shows a simplified subgraph for an IfcWall. During actual deliveries, these properties can be updated automatically by scanning a QR code associated with the batch, further enriching the IFC with logistical attributes and sustainability data. Figure 4 is a subgraph that illustrates how DDT data form a network of interconnected nodes and edges, with an IfcWall in the center linked to the manufacturer details (e.g., Cemex):Property for GWP or recycled content), as well as logistical attributes such as order number and delivery date.

Figure 4. Sample knowledge graph excerpt for a Digital Delivery Ticket. The wall node (IfcWall) connects to manufacturer information and other properties.

4.3. Sample Queries and Results

To demonstrate the effectiveness of the proposed graph-based querying framework, we present selected example queries involving sustainability-relevant properties such as recycled content, manufacturer identity, and material volume. These examples reflect realistic practitioner use cases, such as evaluating compliance with recycled aggregate thresholds or calculating embodied carbon totals from manufacturer-specific data. We used natural language prompts, which the LLM translated into Cypher queries executed on a Neo4j knowledge graph. Table ?? presents two representative queries and their structured execution. More complex multi-hop queries—as summarized in Section 5—further illustrate the advantages of the graph-based approach over direct LLM interpretation of unstructured IFC data.

Table 1. Sample queries executed over a knowledge graph.

Q1: Which materials are recyclable?

(Recycled content > 20%)

```
MATCH (m:ConcreteMaterial)-[:HAS_PROPERTY]->(p:Property)
WHERE p.name = 'RecycledAggregatePercentage'
AND toFloat(p.value) > 20
RETURN m.name AS Material,
p.value AS RecycledPercentage
```

Result: A list of materials whose recycled aggregate content exceeds 20%.

Q2: Total volume of walls by Cemex?

```
MATCH (w:IfcWall)-[:HAS_PROPERTY]->(p:Property)
WHERE p.name = 'Manufacturer'
AND toLower(p.value) CONTAINS 'cemex'
WITH w
MATCH (w)-[:HAS_PROPERTY]->(vol:Property)
WHERE vol.name = 'Volume'
RETURN SUM(toFloat(vol.value)) AS TotalVolume
```

Result: A single numeric value representing the total volume of Cemex-manufactured walls.

5. Results and Discussion

We compared two retrieval pipelines on 12 queries of varying complexity: (i) **Graph-Based**, where an LLM produces queries against a graph database, and (ii) **Direct LLM**, where the model sees flattened IFC text. Table 2 summarises overall performance.

Table 2. Answer accuracy and relationship capture

Method	Accuracy (%)	Relationship capture
Graph-Based	75.0	Moderate/High
Direct LLM	16.7	Low

5.1. Error analysis of the failure cases

1. **Missing semantic enrichment** – The query “elements with 25% recycled aggregates” failed because recycled percentage was absent for two composite materials.
2. **Sparse relationship edges** – The site-address query failed because the IFC entity in one of the models missing Location property, resulting in a null value.
3. **LLM translation drift** – A date filter was mis-parsed as a string literal, resulting zero match.

6. Conclusion and Future Research

We have presented a framework that transforms IFC data into a knowledge graph and use LLMs to answer natural-language queries. Its effectiveness depends on well-defined property sets and sufficiently detailed schema prompts. By exploiting the hierarchy of the IFC schema, the graph representation retrieves information without additional model training and preserves geometric and topological relationships. This structure is especially effective for multi-hop queries involving multiple entities. However, for one-hop questions that require exact question-relation matching, pure LLM retrieval can still be advantageous [12]. By unifying geometry, topology, and lifecycle attributes in a single semantic graph and enabling chat-style natural language queries, the framework significantly enhances accessibility—directly addressing the integration and usability challenges discussed in Section 2. Practitioners without technical knowledge of the IFC schema or query languages can retrieve specific, actionable insights without writing code or navigating complex data hierarchies. This lowers the entry barrier for sustainability professionals, procurement officers, and construction managers who need to engage with BIM data but lack expertise in formal data querying or software engineering.

Future work can integrate Graph Neural Networks (GNNs) for enhanced multi-hop retrieval while retaining the strengths of graph-based search. Incorporating unstructured data (e.g., PDFs, reports) and techniques like GNN-RAG [12] would enable richer insights by linking IFC information with advanced NLP methods (e.g., named entity recognition, dependency parsing). The IFC Whisperer approach—pre-configured with ontological knowledge—will be integrated into the real estate information management solution RE Suite, offering IFC-model visualization alongside a chat interface for natural language queries. A structured pipeline will also organize inspection reports and align them with RE Suite semantics, enhancing unstructured data handling for effective decision-making in real estate management.

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